

Review

Shellfish processing wastewater: characterization of a group of wastewater resources for future valorisation

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ABSTRACT

The seafood processing industry generates large volumes of wastewaters that are released to the environment following variable treatment processes. The composition of shellfish (e.g., mussel, crab) processing wastewater is dependent on the processing technology used, shellfish species and quantities processed, as well as the final desired food product, among other factors. Mussel processing wastewater, for example, can contain up to 860 mg L⁻¹ biochemical oxygen demand (BOD₅), 250 mg L⁻¹ ammonia (NH₃-N) and ammonium (NH₄-N), 2000 mg L⁻¹ total nitrogen (TN), 2400 mg L⁻¹ sulphates (SO₄²⁻) and 20 g L⁻¹ chloride (Cl⁻). This review reveals marked differences in concentrations of BOD₅, chemical oxygen demand (COD), total suspended solids (TSS), NH₃-N, and fats, oils and grease (FOG) in the processing wastewaters from different shellfish group of species. Ranked from high to low concentration are wastewaters from: mussel > crab > fish > scallop > shrimp > clam > sea snail > oyster > lobster ≥ squid. In most cases, concentrations exceed the international standards and limits for effluent discharges. Yet, this study shows that processing wastewater is a rich source of nutrients and minerals that can be utilised. Another innovative approach is to cultivate complementary species, e.g., plants or algae, on wastewater resulting in remediation and valorisation. These approaches are aligned with circular economy principles and can contribute towards the goal of a zero-waste industry.

1. Introduction

Aquaculture is the fastest growing food producing industry and represents an efficient means to provide sustainable food to populations worldwide (Taylor et al., 2013; FAO, 2022). Aquatic products are considered highly nutritious due to the contents of, amongst others, micro-nutrients, essential fatty acids, and amino acids (Taylor et al., 2013; Loaiza et al., 2020). Nevertheless, there are concerns about environmental impacts of aquaculture production relating to both culturing, as well as processing activities of these freshwater and/or marine species.

Shellfish are commonly defined by fisheries, aquaculture and food industries as exoskeleton-bearing aquatic invertebrate organisms which are edible, while seafood is any fish and/or shellfish from the sea used for food (Loaiza et al., 2018). Shellfish aquaculture generates food, animal feed and other products. Large scale cultivation of some shellfish species is an emerging and rapidly expanding industrial activity. For example, the worldwide production of the filter-feeder shellfish mussel (e.g., family Mytilidae) was around 1.5 million tonnes in 2020 and has

increased about two-fold in the last two decades (FAO, 2022; ASC, 2024). One advantage of shellfish (e.g., filter-feeders) production is that the industry is perceived to have fairly minimal impacts on the environment (Parodi et al., 2018), especially in comparison with aquaculture practices for carnivorous fish, shrimp, and other high trophic aquatic species. The production of filter-feeder shellfish does not require high protein diets associated with higher-trophic level organisms (e.g., predatory fish). For example, mussels are filter-feeding organisms that feed on plankton and other microscopic marine organisms and/or suspended organic matter. As a result, reduced inputs and subsequently minimal amounts of waste are generated during *in-situ* production (Filgueira et al., 2019). Other reasons why filter-feeder aquaculture is considered to have a low environmental impact are the low land requirement and minimum anthropogenic greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions (Parodi et al., 2018). Indeed, the production of 50 g of protein is associated with emission of 12 kgCO₂e in the case of beef, but just 0.6 kgCO₂e in the case of mussels (Parodi et al., 2018). Nevertheless, although the environmental impacts of shellfish cultivation may be relatively modest, there is a substantial knowledge gap concerning the

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environmental impacts of shellfish processing (Henriksson et al., 2012; Tamburini et al., 2020).

Little has been specifically published about shellfish processing, however a comparison with seafood processing (which includes fish and shellfish) shows that processes and infrastructure configurations can vary significantly across the industry (Jamieson et al., 2017; Venugopal and Sasidharan, 2021). Processing begins with the delivery of the raw and/or alive organisms from the fishing area or aquaculture farm to the processing facility. Shellfish, processing consists of various steps such as cleaning, cooking, cooling, shelling curing, salting, and/or smoking. In Europe and North America, freezing is the most common preservation method, while producers in Asia and Africa prefer methods such as, salting, smoking and drying. Also, in more developed economies, processing of shellfish has diversified particularly into high-value-added products, such as ready-to-eat meals (Jamieson et al., 2017; FAO, 2022). Thus, shellfish processing techniques and procedures vary among countries and continents. Processing consumes large volumes of fresh or seawater, from 10 to 40 m³ per tonne of raw shellfish material processed, and this results in the generation of large quantities of wastewater (Jamieson et al., 2017; Venugopal and Sasidharan, 2021). The volumes and chemical concentrations of these wastewaters depend on the amount of production, type of food product, processing technology used, shellfish species, and other processing variables (Henriksson et al., 2012; Stevens et al., 2018).

A knowledge gap exists concerning the physicochemical composition of shellfish processing wastewater. In comparison, there is a substantial database on the composition of seafood processing wastewater, and this shows that such wastewater has high concentrations of biochemical oxygen demand (BOD₅), chemical oxygen demand (COD), organic matter, total suspended solids (TSS), fats, oils, and grease (FOG), excess nutrients (e.g., ammonia nitrogen and phosphorus) among other chemicals or contaminants. Seafood processing effluents generally are also saline, as sodium chloride is frequently added to remove slime, blood and other substances and to improve the cleaning efficiency as well as water removal (Venugopal and Sasidharan, 2021). In addition, detergents and disinfectants used during cleaning may also be present. Consequently, the direct discharge of seafood processing wastewater has the potential to degrade receiving water environments through localized depletions of dissolved oxygen, eutrophication, and aquatic toxicity (Chowdhury et al., 2010; Jamieson et al., 2017; Venugopal and Sasidharan, 2021). It is now essential to obtain knowledge about the specific-composition of shellfish processing wastewater to ascertain that such wastewater does not have similar negative effects on the receiving water environment.

Shellfish processing wastewater is traditionally disposed of in the environment following appropriate treatment, and in accordance with national and/or municipal regulations. However, this is not always the case and there has been a serious waste disposal problem for the processing industry in different parts of the world (EU, 1998; EPA, 2021; EPA USA, 2024; Jamieson et al., 2017; Guimarães et al., 2018). Furthermore, shellfish processing wastewater is usually of a variable character and in many cases less amenable to treatment in comparison to municipal, agricultural and domestic wastewaters (Aizenchtadt et al., 2008; Jamieson et al., 2017; Venugopal and Sasidharan, 2021). As a result, wastewater treatment tends to add a substantial cost to the industry, with no direct financial benefits despite the presence of potentially valuable compounds.

One typical treatment method has been applied to shellfish processing wastewaters include, for example, anaerobic digestion which can remove high amounts of organic matters (e.g., COD) from canned processing wastewaters to produce biogas (Fra-Vázquez et al., 2020). The removal efficiencies can be up to 97 % for organic loads from wastewaters of 1–4 kg COD/(m³.d) (Panpong et al., 2014; Sillapacharoenkul and Sinbuathong, 2020). Other new treatment methods tend to be more focused on the production of volatile fatty acids (VFA) from mussel cooking wastewater, this VFA are short-chain fatty acids that are

obtained as metabolic intermediates in the anaerobic digestion that has many applications for different industries (e.g., biofuels, bioplastics, food additives, among others) (Fra-Vázquez et al., 2020). This is reflective of a desire to valorise the remediation of shellfish processing wastewaters as a means to off-set the cost of cleaning wastewaters.

In the coming decades, the global human population is expected to dramatically increase (i.e., predicted to be up to 10.4 billion by 2100) and the sustainable supply of resources has become a serious concern (UN, 2024). The Circular Economy (CE) approach tries to reduce the use of raw resources through re-using, recycling and repairing, whilst turning any waste into new resources, thus closing loops in industrial ecosystems (Stahel, 2016). To adequately implement CE principles, it is necessary to develop pre-requisite knowledge of waste materials. In order to facilitate future studies on wastewater valorisation as part of a CE approach, this review aimed to characterize the physicochemical composition of shellfish processing wastewater.

2. Methodology

2.1. Data analysis

The literature was systematically searched using Google Scholar. Only peer-reviewed articles that appeared also in the databases of Thomson Reuters Web of Science or Scopus (Elsevier) were selected for inclusion. Additional searches to extract relevant grey literature were performed using the Google search engine (e.g., relevant agency reports). The principal search terms were “*seafood processing wastewater*”, “*shellfish processing wastewater*” and “*mussel and seafood industry effluents*”. In total, thirty-seven research articles were selected for inclusion in this study. Initial screening resulted in ‘45,100’ hits for seafood processing wastewater, ‘38,200’ hits for shellfish processing wastewater processing, and ‘11,900’ hits for mussel and seafood industry effluents. The first 500 articles identified for each of the three primary search terms were screened for inclusion (i.e., total screened articles n = 1500). This approach was deemed valid as subsequent hits beyond the first 500 per search term increasingly lacked relevant information related to shellfish processing wastewater. All searches were completed by November 2024. The search results were examined for analytical data on shellfish processing wastewater. Because of the low numbers of research articles on shellfish processing wastewaters, there was no restriction based on publication year. For more detailed information of the criteria employed for article selection is detailed in the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) flow diagram (Fig. 1).

In addition to a search for papers on the physicochemical composition of shellfish processing wastewater, we also searched for technical, governmental and/or institutional reports (e.g., Environmental Protection Agency (EPA-USA), European Union (EU)) on water standards and emission limits. These reports were mostly found on governmental websites and/or through some of the abovementioned research articles. The most up-to-date information was considered for the water quality standard and emission limits of this review. The regulation in relation to effluents guidelines was prioritized for the comparison with shellfish wastewater quality. Nevertheless, to provide a wider and international approach, and to also cover the major number of physicochemical parameters, other current regulations on water standards for different purposes (e.g., potable water use) were also considered for the respective analysis. See Table 1 for more detailed information.

A total of 495 distinct physicochemical measurements (e.g., concentrations of specific water quality parameters) were extracted from the 37 research articles and assessed. These include data for five different main parameters (BOD₅, COD, TSS, NH₃-N, FOG). Based on the availability of relevant data in the literature, ten seafood groups of species were considered: fish, clam, crab, lobster, mussel, oyster, scallop, sea snail, shrimp and squid. These were either raised through aquaculture or harvested from wild populations. The dataset on mussel

† For † N=1500 is the result of analysing the first 500 articles per search.

* This + 32 abstracts screened were extracted from articles which were in the citation lists of identified (310) articles.

Fig. 1. PRISMA flow diagram visualizing the literature screening process at different phases of the analysis. The screening process led to the identification of a total of N = 37 separate articles or publications that were included in the data (quantitative) analysis.

wastewater composition was relatively comprehensive, comprising a total of 309 measurements, across 24 different parameters (see Supplementary material; Table S2 for more detailed information). Ten of these parameters were included in the comparison of mussel wastewater composition with water standards and/or emission limits (i.e., NH_3 , NH_4 , Total Nitrogen (TN), SO_4^{2-} , pH, BOD_5 , total COD (COD_t), Cl^- , O&G (Oil & Grease) and TSS).

2.2. Statistical analysis

Data analysis was performed using R (4.3.3) software environment (<http://www.R-project.org/>). All quantitative data were standardised, e.g., from mg/L to g/L for BOD_5 . Where data could not be standardised, studies were excluded from the review. The arithmetic mean, standard errors (SE) and range (minimum and maximum) of the concentrations were calculated prior to statistical analysis (see Tables S1 and S2; Supplementary material). At the moment only a modest number of studies have reported the physicochemical composition of shellfish processing wastewater, and this precludes use of more advanced statistical methods, including meta-analysis software. Parameters for which there were fewer than three values available, were not considered for statistical analysis. COD and TSS were the only parameters which were considered for statistical tests as enough quantitative data were available. Independent values per parameter and group of species were

nearly always taken from different research articles thus minimizing the risk of bias towards data generated by one research study. The Shapiro-Wilk test was used to test the normality of the distribution, while Levene's test was used to determine the homogeneity of variances. Data were log-transformed where they did not fulfil assumptions of normality and/or homogeneity. If these assumptions were still not fulfilled following log-transformation, non-parametric analogues tests were used. Main effects such as "group of species" were tested using parametric and/or non-parametric tests. The parametric one-way ANOVA with Tukey multiple comparison test, and the non-parametric Kruskal-Wallis with post hoc non-parametric KruskalMc test function were used to compare differences in physicochemical compositions among seafood processing wastewaters. All data are presented as mean \pm SE.

3. Results

3.1. Fish processing wastewater

Fish processing wastewater was included in this study to facilitate comparisons with shellfish data. For fish processing wastewater, BOD_5 concentrations ranged from 6 to 33,500 mg L^{-1} with a mean concentration of $1862 \pm 556 \text{ mg L}^{-1}$ (Fig. 2A). The COD concentration varied between 50 and 13,180 mg L^{-1} , with a mean concentration of $2750 \pm 532 \text{ mg L}^{-1}$ (Fig. 2B). The TSS concentrations ranged from 4 to 7995 mg L^{-1} , while $\text{NH}_3\text{-N}$ ranged from 0.26 to 18 mg L^{-1} , the mean concentrations were $974 \pm 199 \text{ mg L}^{-1}$ and $5 \pm 2 \text{ mg L}^{-1}$, respectively (Fig. 2C and D). FOG was found to range from 2 to 6160 mg L^{-1} with a mean concentration of $947 \pm 428 \text{ mg L}^{-1}$ (Fig. 2E).

3.2. Shellfish processing wastewater

Crab processing wastewater contained BOD_5 concentrations of up to 14,000 mg L^{-1} , with a mean concentration of $2774 \pm 1131 \text{ mg L}^{-1}$ (Fig. 2A). For COD, the concentrations were from 320 to 29,000 mg L^{-1} , while TSS ranged from 1 to 1192 mg L^{-1} (mean concentration: $383 \pm 94 \text{ mg L}^{-1}$) (Fig. 2B and C). The $\text{NH}_3\text{-N}$ concentration was found to vary between 1 and 250 mg L^{-1} , with a mean concentration of $70 \pm 33 \text{ mg L}^{-1}$, and FOG was found at concentrations up to 220 with a mean concentration of $185 \pm 35 \text{ mg L}^{-1}$ (Fig. 2D and E).

For scallop, the processing wastewater contained BOD_5 concentrations of up to 1250 mg L^{-1} , with a mean concentration of $637 \pm 338 \text{ mg L}^{-1}$ (Fig. 2A), while COD was found in concentrations from 300 to 11,000 mg L^{-1} (mean concentration: $3160 \pm 1626 \text{ mg L}^{-1}$) (Fig. 2B). For TSS and $\text{NH}_3\text{-N}$, concentrations were found in the range between 27 and 4000 mg L^{-1} and 0.4–38 mg L^{-1} , respectively (Fig. 2C and D). The FOG concentrations were up to 25 mg L^{-1} with a mean concentration of $20 \pm 5 \text{ mg L}^{-1}$ (Fig. 2E).

For shrimp processing wastewater, the BOD_5 concentration ranged between 120 and 3158 mg L^{-1} , with a mean concentration of $999 \pm 275 \text{ mg L}^{-1}$ (Fig. 2A), while COD was up to 4870 (mean concentration: $2027 \pm 749 \text{ mg L}^{-1}$) (Fig. 2B). For TSS, concentrations ranged between 54 and 2900 mg L^{-1} , with a mean concentration of $587 \pm 209 \text{ mg L}^{-1}$ (Fig. 2C). The $\text{NH}_3\text{-N}$ and FOG concentrations were between 2 to 14 and 17–700 mg L^{-1} , respectively, while the mean concentrations around 10 and 252 mg L^{-1} (Fig. 2D and E).

Clam processing wastewater contained concentrations of up to 2500 and 4000 mg L^{-1} for BOD_5 and COD, with mean concentrations of $1008 \pm 418 \text{ mg L}^{-1}$ and $1905 \pm 613 \text{ mg L}^{-1}$, respectively (Fig. 2A and B). The TSS concentration was between 55 and 6000 mg L^{-1} , with a mean concentration of $1451 \pm 1141 \text{ mg L}^{-1}$ (Fig. 2C). The $\text{NH}_3\text{-N}$ concentration was 0.06 mg L^{-1} . For FOG, concentrations were in the range between 16 and 50 mg L^{-1} , with a mean concentration of $28 \pm 8 \text{ mg L}^{-1}$ (Fig. 2D and E).

Oyster processing wastewaters exhibited BOD_5 concentrations between 164 and 800 mg L^{-1} , with a mean concentration of $460 \pm 115 \text{ mg L}^{-1}$ (Fig. 2A). COD was found in a range of concentrations between 100

Table 1
International water standards for industrial reuse and effluent discharge.

Standards		European Union ^a	Brazil ^b	EPA USA ^c	Spain ^d	Greece ^e	EPA USA ^f				EPA Ireland ^g	EPA-USA/Ireland ^h			
Parameter	unit	Water standards					Shellfish wastewater discharge standards				Wastewater Discharge standards	Drinking water	A1 waters	A2 waters	A3 waters
						Clam	Oyster	Scallop	Abalone						
BOD ₅	mg O ₂ /L	–	<20	≤30	–	≤10	15	67	–	–	25	–	5	5	7
COD	mg O ₂ /L	–	<50	–	–	–	–	–	–	125	–	–	–	–	40
Oil and Grease (O&G)	mg/L	–	<30	–	–	–	0.6–4.2	1.2–2.4	7.7	2.2	–	–	–	–	–
NH ₃	mg/L	–	<5	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	5	–	–	–	–
TSS	mg/L	–	<20	≤30	<35	≤10	59–90	24–270	6–6.6	27	35	–	–	–	–
Turbidity	NTU	1	–	–	–	≤2	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–
Color	HU	15	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	20	100	150
pH		6.5–9.5	6.0–9.0	6.0–9.0	–	6.0–9.0	6.0–9.0	6.0–9.0	6.0–9.0	6.0–9.0	6.0–9.0	>6.5–9.5	5.5–8.5	5.5–9.0	5.5–9.0
Conductivity	µS/cm ⁻¹ at 20 °C	2500	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	2500	1000	1000	1000
Cl ⁻	mg/L	250	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	250	250	250	250
Aluminium (Al)	mg/L	0.2	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	0.2	–	–	–
Total coliform bacteria	MPN/100 ml	0	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	0	5000	25,000	100,000
Fecal coliform bacteria	MPN/100 ml	0	<1000	≤200	<1000	≤5	–	–	–	–	100,000	0	1000	5000	40,000
NH ₄	mg/L	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	0.2	1.5	4
Barium (Ba)	mg/L	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	0.1	1	1
Boron (B)	mg/L	1.5	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	1	2	2	2
Copper (Cu)	mg/L	2	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	2	0.05	0.1	1
Fluoride (F)	mg/L	1.5	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	1.5	1	1.7	1.7
Iron (Fe)	mg/L	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	0.2	0.2	2	2
Manganese (Mn)	mg/L	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	0.05	0.05	0.3	1
Nitrate (NO ₃)	mg/L	50	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	50	50	50	50
Nitrite (NO ₂)	mg/L	0.5	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	0.5	–	–	–
Nitrogen (N)	mg/L	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	1	2	3
P ₂ O ₅	mg/L	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	0.5	0.7	0.7
Sodium (Na)	mg/L	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	200	–	–	–
SO ₄ ^h	mg/L	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	250	200	200	200
Zinc (Zn)	mg/L	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	3	5	5	–
TN	mg/L	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	10	–	–	–	–
Temperature	C	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	25	–	–	–	–
Fluoride	kg/day	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	160	–	–	–	–

A1 waters: Simple physical treatment and disinfection, e.g., rapid filtration and disinfection.

A2 waters: Normal physical treatment, chemical treatment and disinfection, e.g., prechlorination, coagulation, flocculation, decantation, filtration, disinfection (final chlorination).

A3 waters: Intensive physical and chemical treatment, extended treatment and disinfection, e.g., chlorination to break-point, coagulation, flocculation, decantation, filtration, adsorption (activated carbon), disinfection (ozone, final chlorination).

^a European Standard for potable water (EU, 1998; EU, 2020).

^b Brazilian standard for treated effluent discharged to surface waters (Brazil, 1997).

^c USA standards for water reuse in cooling towers (EPA USA, 2012).

^d Spanish standard for water reuse in industrial cleaning processes (Spain, 2007).

^e Greek standard for wastewater reuse as cooling water (Greece, 2011).

^f Effluent Guidelines and Standards for seafood processing industry (EPA USA, 2024).

^g Code of conduct - Domestic (Urban) wastewater discharge standards (EPA, 2021).

^h The water categories in the 1975 Surface Water Directive/1989 Regulations. Definition of the standard methods of treatment for transforming surface water of categories A1, A2 and A3 into drinking water is as follows (EPA, 2001).

Fig. 2. Concentrations of the main wastewater parameters: A) BOD₅, B) COD, C) TSS, D) NH₃-N and E) FOG in different shellfish processing wastewaters. Different letters indicate statistical differences ($p < 0.05$) among groups of seafood species.

N.D.: Not data available. Data on replication and references can be found in the Supplementary material; [Table S1](#).

†Parameter concentrations were based on [Claggett, 1972](#); [Brodersen \(1973\)](#); [Horn and Pohland \(1973\)](#); [Riddle and Shikaze \(1973\)](#); [Pesonen et al. \(1974\)](#); [Welsh and Zall \(1979\)](#); [Chao et al., 1980](#); [Stone et al. \(1981\)](#); [Tilsworth and Morgan \(1983\)](#); [Ziminska \(1985\)](#); [Krofta et al. \(1988\)](#); [Del Valle and Aguilera \(1990\)](#); [Gates \(1991\)](#); [Okumura and Uetana \(1992\)](#); [Tay et al. \(2004\)](#); [Sirianuntapiboon and Srikul \(2006\)](#); [Sridang et al. \(2006\)](#); [Lalonde et al. \(2007\)](#); [Jamieson et al., 2017](#); [Venugopal and Sasidharan \(2021\)](#).

and 2000 mg L⁻¹ (mean concentration 691 ± 445 mg L⁻¹) (Fig. 2B). For TSS, the concentrations were between 50 and 2280 mg L⁻¹, with a mean concentration of 963 ± 484 mg L⁻¹ (Fig. 2C). The NH₃-N concentration was up to 20 mg L⁻¹, with a mean concentration of 15 ± 5 mg L⁻¹ (Fig. 2D). FOG concentrations were between 10 and 30 mg L⁻¹ (Fig. 2E).

For sea snail processing wastewater, BOD₅ and COD concentrations were up to 580 and 1000 mg L⁻¹, respectively, with mean concentrations of 505 ± 75 mg L⁻¹ and 900 ± 100 mg L⁻¹, respectively (Fig. 2A and B). The TSS concentration ranged between 300 and 2000 mg L⁻¹ (mean concentration 1150 ± 850 mg L⁻¹) (Fig. 2C). FOG was present in concentrations up to 30 mg L⁻¹, with a mean concentration of 26 ± 4 mg L⁻¹ (Fig. 2E).

Squid and lobster processing wastewaters contained 11–27 mg L⁻¹ and 24–1205 mg L⁻¹ BOD₅, respectively (mean concentrations 19 ± 8 mg L⁻¹ for squid and 510 ± 221 mg L⁻¹ for lobster) (Fig. 2A). For squid, COD was found in concentrations between 27 and 119 mg L⁻¹, with a mean concentration of 73 ± 46 mg L⁻¹. For lobster, the mean concentration was 922 mg L⁻¹ (Fig. 2B). Lobster cooking wastewater contained concentrations of TSS in the range between 10 and 174 mg L⁻¹, with a mean concentration of 92 ± 30 mg L⁻¹ (Fig. 2C). NH₃-N concentrations were up to 1.5 mg L⁻¹, with a mean concentration of 0.8 ± 0.4 mg L⁻¹ (Fig. 2D).

Mussel processing wastewater contained concentrations of BOD₅ ranging between 66 and 860 mg L⁻¹, with a mean concentration of 259 ± 152 mg L⁻¹ (Fig. 2A). The COD concentration was up to 84,510 mg L⁻¹ with a mean concentration of 17,981 ± 3583 mg L⁻¹ (Fig. 2B). For

TSS, concentrations were in the range between 180 and 4300 mg L⁻¹ (mean concentration: 1542 ± 224 mg L⁻¹), while NH₃-N was present in concentrations from 2 to 312 mg L⁻¹ (mean concentration of 145 ± 90 mg L⁻¹) (Fig. 2C and D). FOG was found in a range of concentrations between 480 and 3760 mg L⁻¹ (Fig. 2E).

When more specific physicochemical parameters were considered for mussel processing wastewater, this wastewater seemed to be particularly rich in COD compounds (e.g., carbohydrate COD (CODcho), CODt, suspended COD (CODs)) with concentrations up to 90 g L⁻¹ (Fig. 3A). Concentrations of O&G, TSS, volatile suspended solids (VSS) and volatile fatty acids (VFAs) were in concentrations up to ~5 g L⁻¹ (Fig. 3A). Proteins, the amino acid taurine, glycogen and sugars were also found in concentrations between 3 and 30 g L⁻¹ (Fig. 3A). The ammonia (NH₃-N), ammonium (NH₄-N) and total nitrogen (TN) concentrations were considerable, ranging between 50 and 250 mg L⁻¹ for the former two parameters, while TN was present in concentrations up to 2000 mg L⁻¹ (Fig. 3B). For ortho-phosphate (PO₄³⁻) and total phosphorus (TP), average concentrations were about 75 mg L⁻¹, while the sulphate (SO₄²⁻) were present in concentrations between 700 and 2400 mg L⁻¹ in mussel processing wastewater (Fig. 3B).

The high variability in physicochemical content of the different shellfish processing wastewaters makes comparisons difficult. Mussel processing wastewater is the only processing wastewater that contained significantly (Kruskal Wallis; $p < 0.05$) higher concentrations of COD than other seafood processing wastewaters, i.e., fish, oyster and squid (Fig. 2B). A similar pattern was found for TSS which was also present in

Fig. 3. Concentrations of key water quality parameters A) in $g L^{-1}$ and B) in $mg L^{-1}$ - in mussel processing wastewater.

*Axis values are pH units.

Data on replication and references can be found in the Supplementary material; Table S2.

†Parameter concentrations were based on Mendez et al. (1992); Murado et al. (1993); Soto et al. (1993); Mendez et al. (1995); Omil et al. (1995); Cros et al. (2004); Omil et al. (2004); Rollón (2005); Lalonde et al. (2007); Barros et al. (2009); Iribarren et al. (2010a); Iribarren et al. (2010b); Iribarren et al. (2010c); Amado and Vázquez, 2015; Jamieson et al., 2017; Fra-Vázquez et al. (2020); Pedrouso et al. (2020); Roibás-Rozas et al. (2020); Gutierrez et al. (2024).

significantly (Kruskal Wallis; $p < 0.05$) higher concentrations in mussel processing wastewater compared to the processing wastewaters from the crab, fish and lobster industry (Fig. 2C).

4. Discussion

4.1. Variation between different groups of seafood species

A literature review has revealed that a broad set of shellfish wastewater parameters has been reported. However, there is no standardised approach and some parameters are not, or rarely reported. This knowledge gap includes the electrical conductivity and the contents of key salts, the sodium absorption ratio, contents of metals, persistent organic pollutants, pathogens and the pH. The most frequently reported parameters detailing the composition of shellfish processing wastewater are BOD₅, COD, TSS, NH₃-N and FOG. Mussel, crab and fish processing wastewater contain the highest concentrations of these parameters, while the wastewaters from sea snail, oyster, lobster and squid processing have the lowest concentrations. Scallop, shrimp and clam processing wastewaters exhibited medium concentrations of contaminants

such as BOD₅, COD, TSS, NH₃-N and FOG compared to other seafood processing waters. Overall, the processing wastewaters can be categorised in the following order, from the most concentrated to the least concentrated wastewater (average BOD₅, COD, TSS, NH₃-N, FOG): mussel > crab > fish > scallop > shrimp > clam > sea snail > oyster > lobster ≥ squid.

It is noteworthy that four of the species groups studied are filter-feeder shellfish, i.e., clam, mussel, oyster and scallop. The commercial interest and consumption of these shellfish is increasing, and their cultivation is considered sustainable (Parodi et al., 2018; Filgueira et al., 2019). However, this study shows that the industrial processing of mussel can give rise to wastewaters with high levels of contaminants. In most cases these wastewaters are more concentrated than those of, for example, fish, crab and shrimp processing. Except for the hard exterior shell, mussels are shellfish consumed 'whole' or 'in toto', whereby the edible portion includes all the soft tissues (e.g., gills, intestine, muscle). Hence the entire organism is processed and commonly cooked in saline solution before it is packed for distribution and consumption (Iribarren et al., 2010c). The chemical composition of processing wastewaters generated during cooking reflects the extensive processing of mussels. In

comparison, other shellfish products, such as oysters and lobsters, are mostly commercialized raw and fresh resulting in less polluted wastewaters (Chandurvelan et al., 2015; Nguyen et al., 2017; Campbell et al., 2022).

The environmental conditions where the shellfish are cultured, either in an aquaculture farm or in the wild, explain in part the chemical composition in these organisms and their processing wastewater. For example, mussels, crabs and shrimps are typically grown in coastal and/or estuarine environments enriched in organic matter, and hence these organisms are cultured on a rich-organic diet. These conditions can influence the resulting processing wastewater, leading to a wastewater rich in organic and other compounds (e.g., BOD, COD, NH₃-N) (Cheng et al., 2020). In comparison, other shellfish that are cultured in more oceanic or offshore environments, e.g., squid and scallops are less likely to have been exposed to dissolved organic matter (Nirmal et al., 2020; Nanda et al., 2021).

Crabs are commonly processed for crab meat, which is extracted from the cooked claws, legs and body. This process generates a considerable amount of waste (almost the entire cephalothorax per crab and the viscera) that contribute to a high concentration of some chemicals (e.g., COD, NH₃-N) in the processing wastewater (Nanda et al., 2021).

A further explanation for the high concentration of NH₃-N present in some shellfish processing wastewaters relates to the cultivation conditions of the specific-shellfish (e.g., crab, shrimp). A high intensity cultivation method might increase the amount of NH₃-N in the surrounding environment and in the shellfish product, and become reflected in the processing wastewaters (Iber and Kasan, 2021; Lin et al., 2022).

4.2. Variation between different wastewaters

A pertinent question concerns the relative strength of shellfish processing wastewater compared to other wastewaters. Two common wastewaters, produced in large amounts, e.g., dairy processing wastewater and domestic wastewater, were considered for comparison with shellfish processing wastewater, focussing on COD, BOD₅, NH₄-N, Cl⁻, and O&G. Dairy processing wastewaters tend to contain high concentrations COD, ranging from 2000 up to 70,150 mg L⁻¹ (Kolev Slavov, 2017; Walsh et al., 2022). These waste concentrations are similar to those found in some types of shellfish processing wastewater (e.g., crab, mussel, scallop) which range up to 30,000 mg L⁻¹. Yet, while COD in dairy processing wastewater can be explained by the presence of lactose (Kolev Slavov, 2017), in the case of shellfish or seafood processing wastewater COD is associated mainly with blood, viscera and solids released during the butchering process (Tay et al., 2004; Jamieson et al., 2017).

Dairy processing wastewater contains similar concentrations of ammonium (64–270 mg L⁻¹ NH₄-N) (Kolev Slavov, 2017; Walsh, 2020) as mussel processing wastewater (230 mg L⁻¹). Dairy processing wastewater also contains slightly higher concentrations of phosphate (20–356 mg L⁻¹) compared to mussel wastewaters (40–160 mg L⁻¹) (Kolev Slavov, 2017; Walsh et al., 2022). However, mussel processing wastewaters contain high concentrations of NaCl (17–22 g L⁻¹ or ppt, including 5596–8000 mg L⁻¹ Na and 8000 to 19,940 mg L⁻¹ Cl⁻) (Fig. 2 and Supplementary material; Table 2S). These elevated salt concentrations are explained by washing of this marine species with saltwater during processing (Jamieson et al., 2017). Dairy processing wastewaters contain up to 35-fold lower Na and Cl⁻ concentrations (250–986 Na mg L⁻¹ and 525–1349 Cl⁻ mg L⁻¹) compared to mussel wastewaters (Kolev Slavov, 2017; Walsh, 2020). This latter observation has major implications for remediation of shellfish processing wastewaters, as any biological process will need to be mediated by halophyte species.

Domestic wastewaters, collected from individual households, can contain COD concentrations ranging from 300 to 1000 mg L⁻¹ (EPA, 2021). These concentrations are similar to those in oyster, sea snail and

squid processing wastewater. As a case study, domestic wastewaters from Shanghai, China were analysed for their organic matter composition. COD_t and CODs concentrations were around 204–440 mg L⁻¹ and 108–372 mg L⁻¹, respectively (Huang et al., 2010), while mussel processing wastewaters contain concentrations up to 84,000 mg COD_t L⁻¹ and 93,000 mg CODs L⁻¹. A similar pattern was found for protein COD (COD_{protein}), lipids COD (COD_{lipids}), VFA and sugars, with concentrations ranging between 2.9 and 39.47 mg L⁻¹ in domestic wastewaters (Huang et al., 2010), whereas in mussel processing wastewaters concentrations range between 25 and 26,000 mg L⁻¹, i.e., hundreds, and even thousand-fold higher. Domestic wastewaters typically contain concentrations of 150–500 mg L⁻¹ BOD₅ (EPA, 2021), which is considerably lower than found in shellfish processing wastewater. The TSS concentration in domestic wastewaters ranges between 200 and 700 mg L⁻¹ (EPA, 2021), which is also up to 10-times lower than found in some shellfish processing wastewaters, e.g., clam, mussel, among others.

4.3. Standards and limits

In the present study readily accessible standards and limits were considered from multiple jurisdictions (see Table 1), and these were compared with pollutant concentrations found in mussel processing wastewater. Notably, the Environmental Protection Agency (EPA-USA) sets standards and limits for seafood processing wastewaters that are frequently adopted worldwide by regulatory bodies operating in different jurisdictions. From the ten concentration parameters assessed in mussel processing wastewater, only three (pH, COD_t, O&G) gave concentrations which are under the regulatory threshold concentration (Fig. 4).

Mussel processing wastewater exceeds the threshold for NH₄ (0.2 mg L⁻¹ as per EPA-USA/Ireland) by up to ~1130-times (Fig. 4b). The TSS concentration (e.g., 4.3 g L⁻¹) in mussel processing wastewater exceeds by 716-times the emission standard (0.06 g L⁻¹ as per EPA-USA) (Fig. 4i). Concentrations of NH₃, Total Nitrogen, SO₄²⁻, BOD₅ and Cl⁻ in mussel wastewaters, compared to the strictest regulations, exceeded emission thresholds by up to 200-fold (Fig. 4). Individual wastewater samples can in some cases pass the emission standards, yet average concentrations in mussel processing wastewater exceed the threshold even in case of the least strict standard (Fig. 4). This emphasises the need to remediate shellfish wastewaters negative impacts on receiving aquatic ecosystems. It is well known that the continuous discharge of mussel processing wastewater with high levels of TSS (e.g., ~1.5 g L⁻¹), BOD₅ (e.g., ~0.2 g L⁻¹) may cause hypoxia or even anoxia resulting in the death of aquatic organisms. Furthermore, high levels of nitrogenous wastes, e.g., TN, NH₃, NH₄ may lead to eutrophication, ecotoxicity risks, biotic depletion, water acidification and indirectly disease outbreaks (Venugopal and Sasidharan, 2021; Mahari et al., 2022).

The release of mussel wastewaters with high SO₄²⁻ concentrations, up to 2400 mg L⁻¹ can potentially affect water quality and aquatic ecosystems, potentially even impacting on human health. High levels of SO₄²⁻, above emission standards can change water chemistry, including the biochemical sulphur cycle, increase water salinity and promote formation of toxic compounds, e.g., hydrogen sulfide that can negatively affect living organisms (Li et al., 2025). Drastic changes of pH in water bodies such as coastal ecosystems can also negatively affect water chemistry, amongst others through effects on the solubility of heavy metals, with potential effects on aquatic life. Mussel processing wastewaters showed pH concentrations above 9, which exceeded the emission standards and those found in coastal ecosystems (pH: ~8), therefore the continuous discharge of this wastewater can increase the pH variability of this ecosystem and harm fish and other coastal organisms in the long term (Carstensen and Duarte, 2019).

In seafood processing factories, including mussel processing plants, the most common products for cleaning and processing (e.g., hypochlorite) contain Cl⁻. Therefore, levels up to 20 g Cl L⁻¹ were found in

Fig. 4. Concentration of specific chemical parameters in mussel processing wastewater relative to their respective international standards and/or limits. Box-plots represent specific concentrations identified in this review. Standards and/or limits are indicated by dotted lines. For a) NH_3 (---; Brazilian standard), b) NH_4 (--- EPA-USA/Ireland; --- EPA-USA/Ireland; --- EPA-USA/Ireland), c) Total Nitrogen (---; EPA Ireland), d) BOD_5 (--- EPA-USA^f; --- EPA-USA^f; --- EPA-USA^c), e) COD_t (---; EPA-USA/Ireland ---; Brazilian standard), f) Cl^- (---; EPA-USA/Ireland and EU), g) O&G (--- EPA USA^f; --- EPA USA^f; --- Brazilian standard), h) TSS (--- EPA USA^f; --- EPA USA^f; --- EPA USA^c) and i) pH (--- EPA-USA/Ireland; --- EPA-USA^f; --- EPA-USA^f). Red, blue and green dotted lines indicate the level of regulation, e.g., red is for the strictest (or lowest concentration permitted) regulation, blue for the medium strict regulation, while green represents the most permissible regulation. EPA-USA^c: USA standards for water reuse in cooling towers, EPA USA^f: Effluent Guidelines and Standards for seafood processing industry.

mussel wastewater, which is high, even similar to the Cl^- concentrations from metallurgic wastewater industries (Duan et al., 2024). High levels of Cl^- in different forms can increase mineralization of aquatic environments, posing a threat to freshwater organisms adapted to low salinity conditions. In addition, the mineral Cl^- can directly cause toxicity in fish, plankton and the entire aquatic food web, impacting survival and reproduction (Duan et al., 2024).

The water quality emission standards vary among countries and regions. In some countries, some parameters are strictly regulated while in other geographical locations this is less the case. This review shows some examples for countries such as Spain, USA, Brazil and Greece, for which the standards or limits for some chemicals are similar, while others differ around 3-fold. For example, the TSS limits from USA is 3-fold more than the TSS limits from Greece or EU. Therefore, seafood or shellfish industries will have different criteria concerning the environmental management of their wastewaters depending on the location of production. It is also noteworthy to mention that the monitoring and enforcement capacity is likely to vary per country. In some developing countries the capacity for supervision, sampling and water analysis can be minimal due to the lack of monetary resources, which leads to poor regulation of the industry, with possible consequences for water quality in these countries (Solsona, 2002). Nevertheless, this review article tries to give a wide picture of the shellfish processing wastewater parameter levels compared with international regulations in order to implement more sustainable solutions.

4.4. Wastewater valorisation towards a circular economy approach

Despite culturing of shellfish being deemed relatively 'environmentally friendly', processing of shellfish results in a large amount of contaminated wastewater (Figs. 2 and 3) which contain contaminants such as minerals, fats, proteins, and sugars. Current wastewater treatment practices employed to clean wastewater to regulatory standards tend to be efficient but can be costly and an economic burden to the industry. Moreover, attempts to valorise contaminants are typically lacking. A complicating factor is that the composition of processing wastewater is variable, and will therefore affect its utilization. For example, the origin of the shellfish can affect possible valorisation of processing wastewater as shellfish produced in aquaculture facilities might contain higher concentrations of some chemicals and/or contaminants than shellfish harvested from the wild (Wu and Yang, 2011). Therefore, remediation and possible utilization of shellfish wastewaters needs to relate to the origin of the shellfish product and its cultivation conditions.

Given the complexity of shellfish processing wastewater, it is likely that an integrated cascading system will be required to remediate and valorise wastewater. A cascading system is a central concept of integrated biorefineries, which focuses on the integration of multiple biomass conversion technologies to convert feedstocks into a range of value-added products (Ng et al., 2017). Valuable compounds, including proteins, can be isolated using well established techniques such as alkaline extraction and isoelectric precipitation. Microbial technology can be used for the recovery of other organic compounds. These compounds can be converted to bioenergy or biopolymers including feedstocks for biodegradable plastics (Puyol et al., 2017). For example, anaerobic microbial digestion (AD) can convert lipids, proteins and sugars in to either biomethane, or VFAs. The latter can be used as platform chemicals for production of polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs) which are feedstocks for production of bioplastics (Peces et al., 2016).

A subsequent step can involve the use of complementary organisms (e.g., plants or algae) which extract minerals, resulting in the production of valuable biomass (Fig. 5). Saline resistant plants and/or algae are a

Fig. 5. Infographic of the use of saline plants (e.g., *Salicornia* spp.) for the valorisation of shellfish processing wastewater as part of a circular economy approach (1) Shellfish (e.g., mussel). processing wastewater originates at an industrial production site. The processing wastewater high in nutrients and contaminants is (2) treated (e.g., microbial digestion) and then used for (3) plant or algae cultivation where the effluent 1 become effluent 2, and (4) part of these nutrients and contaminants will be removed by plants or algae, thus lowering concentrations below respective standards. (5) The plant/algal biomass can then be used as raw material for the extraction of valuable elements and compounds (e.g., proteins, oils, minerals).

potential target group of species for this purpose (Vo et al., 2020; Khalilzadeh et al., 2021). For example, the plant *Salicornia europaea* L, and the algae *Dunaliella salina* can be grown on different types of wastewaters including domestic, marine aquaculture, and industrial wastewaters (Liu and Yildiz, 2018; Vo et al., 2020; Khalilzadeh et al., 2021). *Salicornia* spp. are resistant, adaptative and resilient species that can grow in harsh (e.g., hypersaline and/or polluted) environments (Khalilzadeh et al., 2021; Yasseen and Al-Thani, 2022). *S. europaea* produces edible shoots and phytoremediates the medium (i.e., saline wastewater) by removing excessive concentrations of nutrients and other contaminants (Khalilzadeh et al., 2021). Algae can similarly tolerate different saline concentrations and are suitable for saline wastewater treatment. Algal biomass can be used as feedstock, biofuel, biomaterial, and for health-care/medical purposes (Vo et al., 2020). The microalgae *D. salina* has been used for municipal wastewater remediation, where it removed 45–88 % of the nitrate, ammonia and phosphorus, and demonstrated best growth on a saline medium (Liu and Yildiz, 2018).

Shellfish processing wastewaters are saline, limiting biological treatment to halophytes. However, salt-specific extraction techniques are being developed, and can open-up remediation to freshwater species. For example, diffusion dialysis can remove Cl⁻ with a removal efficiency as high as 50–70 %, while the zinc loss is less than 1 % (Li et al., 2022). This approach would enable direct extraction of valuable minerals from shellfish processing wastewaters, and/or enable cultivation of a much wider variety of freshwater algae and plants on shellfish processing wastewater, including duckweed species, the remediation potential of which has been well established (Zhou and Borisjuk, 2019; Paolacci et al., 2022).

Other technologies can also be considered for remediation of these saline wastewaters, such as ultrafiltration, electrodialysis, modified thermal and membrane-based techniques (Darre and Toor, 2018; Elsaid et al., 2020). These technologies could play a crucial role to reduce the salt and mineral concentrations from these seafood processing wastewaters, which may support circular economies through reuse and utilization. Various membrane technologies offer a promising and innovative solution for the treatment of saline wastewaters, such as shellfish processing wastewater. Currently, it is common to use integrated membrane processes for efficient separation applications, e.g., pressure-driven membrane filtration, reverse osmosis, membrane bioreactor treatment, for saline wastewater treatment (Ahmad et al.,

2021). For example, activated carbon reverse osmosis integrated with an electrodialysis-reversal treatment was found to remove up to 90 % of chlorides and alkalinity from a petrochemical industry wastewater in Brazil (Venzke et al., 2018).

Shellfish processing wastewaters can also be used for agriculture purposes after some treatments (e.g., salt extraction) that can make these wastewaters suitable for the soil and crops. The N:P ratio found in shellfish wastewaters based on TN (~1000 mg L⁻¹) and TP (~100 g L⁻¹) was 10:1. This ratio is not in a proper balance for best performance on agriculture, groundwater pollution and eutrophication can occur using this wastewater. In terms of salts, the NaCl concentrations found were about 20 g L⁻¹, which are also not ideal for agriculture purposes. These high levels of salinity can cause toxicity to plants and damage soil structure. Metals and other possible contaminants, e.g., persistent organic pollutants were not found in the literature of shellfish processing wastewaters. However, we measured metals such as Cu and Ni in mussel processing wastewaters, the concentrations were 0.16 and 0.11 mg L⁻¹, respectively (see Table S2; Supplementary material). These two metals concentrations are under or around the limits for Cu (0.5 mg L⁻¹) and Ni (0.1 mg L⁻¹) for industrial effluents. The pH of mussel processing wastewaters found was from about 5.0 to 7.5 on average, which can be slightly alkaline but in the acceptable range for agriculture that cannot affect nutrient availability to plants and soil properties.

Mussel wastewater from canning processing can yield valuable volatile fatty acids (VFA). Despite the complexity of mussel-based wastewater due to high organic matter, high salinity and low pH, it was possible to produce VFA rich streams of 0.72 ± 0.07 g COD_{VFA}/(L·d). The VFA ratios were 80:18:2 for acetic: propionic: butyric acid using mussel wastewater in a bioreactor. The carbohydrate conversion from COD into VFA was up to 96 %. Therefore, this study showed that complex wastewaters, e.g., the mussel processing wastewater can be used to produce valuable compounds such as VFA (Fra-Vázquez et al., 2020). Typical mussel processing wastewaters as identified in the present study, containing high concentrations of fats (i.e., FOG: up to 3760 mg L⁻¹) would be suitable for VFA production, unlike wastewaters from some other shellfish. Thus, knowledge of species-specific characteristic of wastewaters is critical when deciding on its possible utilization.

A successful depuration of shrimp cooking wastewater was conducted using ultrafiltration technology. The recovery of high concentrations of astaxanthin up to 13 µg mL⁻¹ from shrimp processing

wastewater was obtained using by 300 kDa ultrafiltration. The use of membranes from 300, 100 to 30 kDa molecular weight cut-off was the best combination for protein concentration. The hydrolysates prepared from these three protein-concentrated fractions got remarkable antihypertensive and antioxidant activities. Therefore, the shrimp cooking wastewater is a promising source of astaxanthin and bioactive peptides for the possible production of high value-added products (Amado et al., 2016). Finally, chitin and derived sub-products (biopolymers) from shellfish processing waste are also high value commodities, although there are few reports on concentrations of these compounds in shellfish processing wastewater. Chitin and/or chitosan can be used in medicine, food-preparation and in environmental wastewater treatment due to its unique chemical structure and positive charge (Zuo et al., 2001; Ngassotter et al., 2023). All in all, these calculations emphasise that concentrated shellfish processing wastewaters should be considered an opportunity rather than a problem.

5. Conclusion

The shellfish processing industry produces wastewaters with high concentrations of pollutants, similar to other agri-food industries. However, the composition of such wastewaters varies depending on the group of species processed. Mussel and crab are the shellfish which their processing can generate the highest concentrations of BOD₅, COD, TSS, NH₃-N and FOG. Ranked from high to low concentration are wastewaters (incl. fish for comparison) from: mussel > crab > fish > scallop > shrimp > clam > sea snail > oyster > lobster ≥ squid. Mussel processing wastewater exhibits an interesting chemical composition with a) higher salt concentrations than other agri-food wastewaters; b) ammonium levels similar to other agri-food wastewaters; and c) higher concentrations of specific-organic parameters (e.g., CODs, CODt, CODprotein) than domestic wastewaters. Concentrations of various pollutants in mussel processing wastewater exceed water effluent emission limits, typically necessitating costly wastewater treatment. Yet, mussel processing wastewater is not just a problem, but also an opportunity for its utilization through a circular economy approach.

6. Future considerations and perspectives

The shellfish processing wastewaters characterized in this review showed a high variability of chemicals or contaminants. It was found that in many cases contaminant concentrations were above emission standards and limits from different international regulatory institutions. Therefore, it is essential to treat these shellfish wastewaters prior to release in the environment. This paper shows for the first time the shellfish-specific composition of processing wastewater, with substantial differences in concentrations of contaminant depending on the species processed. Thus, it is recommended to adapt shellfish-species specific-remediation treatments. This paper has also found that shellfish processing wastewater contains substantial amounts of oils and greases as well as protein. These contaminants are of commercial interest, and it can be envisaged that through the use of up-to-date recovery and extraction technologies valuable compounds can be produced from shellfish wastewaters as part of a circular economy solution.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Iván Loiza: Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Neil E. Coughlan:** Writing – review & editing. **Gavin Burnell:** Writing – review & editing. **Marcel A.K. Jansen:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2025.127595>.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

References

- Ahmad, N.N.R., Ang, W.L., Leo, C.P., Mohammad, A.W., Hilal, N., 2021. Current advances in membrane technologies for saline wastewater treatment: a comprehensive review. *Desalination* 517, 115170.
- Aizenchtadt, E., Ingman, D., Friedler, E., 2008. Quality control of wastewater treatment: a new approach. *Eur. J. Oper. Res.* 189 (2), 445–458.
- Amado, I.R., Vázquez, J.A., 2015. Mussel processing wastewater: a low-cost substrate for the production of astaxanthin by *Xanthophyllomyces dendrorhous*. *Microb. Cell Fact.* 14 (1), 177.
- Amado, I.R., González, M.P., Murado, M.A., Vázquez, J.A., 2016. Shrimp wastewater as a source of astaxanthin and bioactive peptides. *J. Chem. Technol. Biotechnol.* 91 (3), 793–805.
- ASC, 2024. Aenuaculture stewardship council, 2024. <https://asc-aqua.org/>.
- Barros, M.C., Magán, A., Valiño, S., Bello, P.M., Casares, J.J., Blanco, J.M., 2009. Identification of best available techniques in the seafood industry: a case study. *J. Clean. Prod.* 17 (3), 391–399.
- Brazil, 1997. NBR 13969. Tanque Sépticos: Unidades De Tratamento Complementar E Disposição Final Dos Efluentes - Projeto. Construção E Operação, ABNT (Associação Brasileira de Normas Técnicas), Rio de Janeiro, 1997.
- Brodersen, K.T., 1973. A study of the waste characteristics in fish processing plants located in the maritime region. In: *Water Pollution Control Directorate, EPS 3-WP-7vols. 3–7*. Environmental Protection Service.
- Campbell, V.M., Chouljenko, A., Hall, S.G., 2022. Depuration of live oysters to reduce *Vibrio parahaemolyticus* and *vibrio vulnificus*: a review of ecology and processing parameters. *Compr. Rev. Food Sci. Food Saf.* 21 (4), 3480–3506.
- Carstensen, J., Duarte, C.M., 2019. Drivers of pH variability in coastal ecosystems. *Environ. Sci. Technol.* 53 (8), 4020–4029.
- Chandurvelan, R., Marsden, I.D., Glover, C.N., Gaw, S., 2015. Assessment of a mussel as a metal bioindicator of coastal contamination: relationships between metal bioaccumulation and multiple biomarker responses. *Sci. Total Environ.* 511, 663–675.
- Chao, A.C., Machedehl, J.L., Galarraga, E., 1980. Ultrafiltration treatment of seafood processing wastewaters. In: *Proc., 35th Industrial Waste Conf (Lafayette, IN)*.
- Cheng, H., Jiang, Z.Y., Ma, X.X., Wang, Y.S., 2020. Nitrogen dynamics in the mangrove sediments affected by crabs in the intertidal regions. *Ecotoxicology* 29 (6), 669–675.
- Chowdhury, P., Viraraghavan, T., Srinivasan, A., 2010. Biological treatment processes for fish processing wastewater—A review. *Bioresour. Technol.* 101 (2), 439–449.
- Claggett, F.G., 1972. The use of chemical treatment and air flotation for the clarification of fish processing plant wastewater. In: *Proc 3rd Natl. Symp. Food Processing Waste*, p. 187. Washington, DC.
- Cros, S., Ignot, B.L., Razafintsalama, C., Jaouen, P., Ourseau, P.B., 2004. Electrodialysis desalination and reverse osmosis concentration of an industrial mussel cooking juice: process impact on pollution reduction and on aroma quality. *J. Food Sci.* 69 (6), C435–C442.
- Darre, N.C., Toor, G.S., 2018. Desalination of water: a review. *Curr. Pollut. Rep.* 4, 104–111.

- Del Valle, J.M., Aguilera, J.M., 1990. Recovery of liquid by-products from fishmeal factories: a review. *Process Biochem.* 25 (4), 122–131.
- Duan, L., Yun, Q., Jiang, G., Teng, D., Zhou, G., Cao, Y., 2024. A review of chloride ions removal from high chloride industrial wastewater: sources, hazards, and mechanisms. *J. Environ. Manag.* 353, 120184.
- Elsaid, K., Kamil, M., Sayed, E.T., Abdelkareem, M.A., Wilberforce, T., Olabi, A., 2020. Environmental impact of desalination technologies: a review. *Sci. Total Environ.* 748, 141528.
- EPA USA, 2012. United States Environmental Protection Agency, Guidelines for Water Reuse, EPA/600/R-12/618. Environmental Protection Agency, Washington, D.C., 2012.
- EPA USA, 2024. Environmental Protection Agency, 2024. Code of Federal Regulations. Available at: <https://www.ecfr.gov/current/title-40/chapter-I/subchapter-N/part-408>.
- EPA, 2001. Environmental protection agency. In: Parameters of Water Quality. Interpretation and Standards, 2001.
- EPA, 2021. Environmental protection agency, 2021. Code of conduct - domestic (Urban) wastewater discharge standards. Available at: <https://www.epa.ie/publications/compliance-enforcement/waste-water/2021.CodeofPractice.Web.pdf>.
- EU, 1998. European Union, Council Directive 98/83/EC of 3 November 1998 on the quality of water intended for human consumption. *Off. J. Eur. Commun.* 32–53. L330 (1998).
- EU, 2020. European Union, Directive (EU) 2020/2184 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 16 December 2020 on the Quality of Water Intended for Human Consumption (recast).
- FAO, 2022. The State of World Fisheries and Aquaculture 2022. Towards Blue Transformation. FAO, Rome.
- Filgueira, R., Stropfle, L.C., Strohmeier, T., Rastrick, S., Strand, Ø., 2019. Mussels or tunicates: that is the question. Evaluating efficient and sustainable resource use by low-trophic species in aquaculture settings. *J. Clean. Prod.* 231, 132–143.
- Fra-Vázquez, A., Pedrouso, A., Del Río, A.V., Mosquera-Corral, A., 2020. Volatile fatty acid production from saline cooked mussel processing wastewater at low pH. *Sci. Total Environ.* 732, 139337.
- Gates, K.W., 1991. Waste reduction, water conservation, and recovery of seafood by-products. *Mar. Technol. Sci.* 25 (1), 44–51.
- Greece, 2011. Joint Ministerial Decree (JMD) 145116/2011: Definition of Measures, Conditions and Procedure for Wastewater Reuse, 354B. Greek Government Gazette, 2011) 8/3/2011.
- Guimarães, J.T., Souza, A.L., Brígida, A.I.S., Furtado, A.A., Chicrala, P.C., Santos, V.R., et al., 2018. Quantification and characterization of effluents from the seafood processing industry aiming at water reuse: a pilot study. *J. Water Proc. Eng.* 26, 138–145.
- Gutiérrez, M., San Martín, D., Ibarruri, J., Foti, G., Bald, C., Goienetxea, N., et al., 2024. Recovery of savory compounds from mussel cooking side stream as circular economy solution. *Environ. Chall.* 14, 100840.
- Henriksson, P.J., Guinée, J.B., Kleijn, R., de Snoo, G.R., 2012. Life cycle assessment of aquaculture systems—a review of methodologies. *Int. J. Life Cycle Assess.* 17, 304–313.
- Horn, C.R., Pohland, F.G., 1973. Characterization and treatability of selected shellfish processing wastes. In: *Proc. 28th Ind. Waste Conf. (Lafayette, IN)*.
- Huang, M.H., Li, Y.M., Gu, G.W., 2010. Chemical composition of organic matters in domestic wastewater. *Desalination* 262 (1–3), 36–42.
- Iber, B.T., Kasan, N.A., 2021. Recent advances in Shrimp aquaculture wastewater management. *Heliyon* 7 (11), e08283.
- Iribarren, D., Moreira, M.T., Feijoo, G., 2010a. Implementing by-product management into the life cycle assessment of the mussel sector. *Resour. Conserv. Recycl.* 54 (12), 1219–1230.
- Iribarren, D., Moreira, M.T., Feijoo, G., 2010b. Life cycle assessment of fresh and canned mussel processing and consumption in Galicia (NW Spain). *Resour. Conserv. Recycl.* 55 (2), 106–117.
- Iribarren, D., Moreira, M.T., Feijoo, G., 2010c. Revisiting the life cycle assessment of mussels from a sectorial perspective. *J. Clean. Prod.* 18 (2), 101–111.
- Jamieson, B.L., Gagnon, G.A., Gonçalves, A.A., 2017. Physicochemical characterization of Atlantic Canadian seafood processing plant effluent. *Mar. Pollut. Bull.* 116 (1–2), 137–142.
- Khalilzadeh, R., Pirzad, A., Sepehr, E., Khan, S., Anwar, S., 2021. The *Salicornia europaea* potential for phytoremediation of heavy metals in the soils under different times of wastewater irrigation in northwestern Iran. *Environ. Sci. Pollut. Control Ser.* 28, 47605–47618.
- Kolev Slavov, A., 2017. General characteristics and treatment possibilities of dairy Wastewater—a review. *Food Technol. Biotechnol.* 55 (1), 14–28.
- Krofta, M., Wang, L.K., Pollman, C.D., 1988. Treatment of seafood processing wastewater by dissolved air flotation carbon adsorption and free chlorination. *Proc. 43rd Ind. Waste Conf. (Lafayette, IN)*.
- Lalonde, B., Garron, C.A., Ernst, W., 2007. Characterization and toxicity testing of fish processing plant effluent in Canada. Surveillance report EPS-5-AR-07-03. Environmental Protection report series. Environmental Protection Operations Directorate, Environment Canada Atlantic Region, p. 75.
- Li, J., Han, Z., Yu, J., Tian, Y., 2025. Simulation of water flow and sulfate transport in a large freshwater lake basin under natural and anthropogenic disturbances. *Water Res.*, 123805.
- Li, Y., Yang, Z., Yang, K., Wei, J., Li, Z., Ma, C., et al., 2022. Removal of chloride from water and wastewater: removal mechanisms and recent trends. *Sci. Total Environ.* 821, 153174.
- Lin, W., Luo, H., Wu, J., Hung, T.C., Cao, B., Liu, X., et al., 2022. A review of the emerging risks of acute ammonia nitrogen toxicity to aquatic decapod crustaceans. *Water* 15 (1), 27.
- Liu, Y., Yildiz, I., 2018. The effect of salinity concentration on algal biomass production and nutrient removal from municipal wastewater by *Dunaliella salina*. *Int. J. Energy Res.* 42 (9), 2997–3006.
- Loaiza, I., De Troch, M., De Boeck, G., 2018. Potential health risks via consumption of six edible shellfish species collected from Piura–Peru. *Ecotoxicol. Environ. Saf.* 159, 249–260.
- Loaiza, I., De Troch, M., De Boeck, G., 2020. Marine species as safe source of LC-PUFA and micronutrients: insights in new promising marine food in Peru. *Food Chem.* 321, 126724.
- Mahari, W.A.W., Waiho, K., Azwar, E., Fazhan, H., Peng, W., Ishak, S.D., et al., 2022. A state-of-the-art review on producing engineered biochar from shellfish waste and its application in aquaculture wastewater treatment. *Chemosphere* 288, 132559.
- Mendez, R., Lema, J.M., Soto, M., 1995. Treatment of seafood-processing wastewaters in mesophilic and thermophilic anaerobic filters. *Water Environ. Res.* 67 (1), 33–45.
- Mendez, R., Omil, F., Soto, M., Lema, J.M., 1992. Pilot plant studies on the anaerobic treatment of different wastewaters from a fish-canning factory. *Water Sci. Technol.* 25 (1), 37–44.
- Murado, M.A., Siso, M.I., Gonzalez, M.P., Montemayor, M., Pastrana, L., Pintado, J., 1993. Characterization of microbial biomasses and amyolytic preparations obtained from mussel processing waste treatment. *Bioresour. Technol.* 43 (2), 117–125.
- Nanda, P.K., Das, A.K., Dandapat, P., Dhar, P., Bandyopadhyay, S., Dib, A.L., et al., 2021. Nutritional aspects, flavour profile and health benefits of crab meat based novel food products and valorisation of processing waste to wealth: a review. *Trends Food Sci. Technol.* 112, 252–267.
- Ng, D.K., Ng, K.S., Ng, R.T., 2017. Integrated biorefineries. In: *Encyclopedia of Sustainable Technologies*. Elsevier, pp. 299–314.
- Ngasotter, S., Xavier, K.M., Meitei, M.M., Waikhom, D., Pathak, J., Singh, S.K., 2023. Crustacean shell waste derived chitin and chitin nanomaterials for application in agriculture, food, and health—A review. *Carbohydrate Polymer Technologies and Applications*, 100349.
- Nguyen, T.T., Barber, A.R., Corbin, K., Zhang, W., 2017. Lobster processing by-products as valuable bioresource of marine functional ingredients, nutraceuticals, and pharmaceuticals. *Bioresour. Technol.* 4, 1–19.
- Nirmal, N.P., Santivarangkna, C., Rajput, M.S., Benjakul, S., 2020. Trends in shrimp processing waste utilization: an industrial prospective. *Trends Food Sci. Technol.* 103, 20–35.
- Okumura, A., Uetana, K., 1992. Treatment of fish processing wastes in Japan. *Ind. Environ.* 15, 1–2.
- Omil, F., García-Sandá, E., Méndez, R., Lema, J.M., 2004. Clean technologies for wastewater management in seafood canning industries. Technological choices for sustainability 103–125.
- Omil, F., Méndez, R., Lema, J.M., 1995. Anaerobic treatment of saline wastewaters under high sulphide and ammonia content. *Bioresour. Technol.* 54 (3), 269–278.
- Panpong, K., Srisuwan, G., Sompong, O., Kongjan, P., 2014. Anaerobic co-digestion of canned seafood wastewater with glycerol waste for enhanced biogas production. *Energy Proc.* 52, 328–336.
- Paolacci, S., Stejskal, V., Toner, D., Jansen, M.A., 2022. Integrated multitrophic aquaculture; analysing contributions of different biological compartments to nutrient removal in a duckweed-based water remediation system. *Plants* 11 (22), 3103.
- Parodi, A., Leip, A., De Boer, I.J.M., Slegers, P.M., Ziegler, F., Temme, E.H., et al., 2018. The potential of future foods for sustainable and healthy diets. *Nat. Sustain.* 1 (12), 782–789.
- Peces, M., Astals, S., Clarke, W.P., Jensen, P.D., 2016. Semi-aerobic fermentation as a novel pre-treatment to obtain VFA and increase methane yield from primary sludge. *Bioresour. Technol.* 200, 631–638.
- Pedrouso, A., Fra-Vázquez, A., Val del Río, A., Mosquera-Corral, A., 2020. Recovery of polyhydroxyalkanoates from cooked mussel processing wastewater at high salinity and acidic conditions. *Sustainability* 12 (24), 10386.
- Pesenon, I.B., Porkhal, E.V., Baranova, A.P., Zhabbarov, A.N., 1974. Composition of wastewater from fish-processing plants. *Chem. Abstr.* 81 (175709n).
- Puyol, D., Batstone, D.J., Hülsen, T., Astals, S., Peces, M., Krömer, J.O., 2017. Resource recovery from wastewater by biological technologies: opportunities, challenges, and prospects. *Front. Microbiol.* 7, 2106.
- Riddle, M.J., Shikaze, K., 1973. Characterization and treatment of fish processing plant effluents in Canada. In: *Proc. 4th National Symposium on Food Processing Wastes*. Washington, DC.
- Roibás-Rozas, A., Mosquera-Corral, A., Hospido, A., 2020. Environmental assessment of complex wastewater valorisation by polyhydroxyalkanoates production. *Sci. Total Environ.* 744, 140893.
- Rollón, A.P., 2005. Anaerobic Digestion of Fish Processing Wastewater with Special Emphasis on Hydrolysis of Suspended Solids, vol. 19. CRC Press.
- Sillapacharoenkul, B., Sinbuathong, N., 2020. Anaerobic biological treatment of frozen seafood wastewater. *Environ. Prog. Sustain. Energy* 39 (5), e13418.
- Sirianuntapiboon, S., Srikul, M., 2006. Reducing red color intensity of seafood wastewater in facultative pond. *Bioresour. Technol.* 97 (14), 1612–1617.
- Solsona, F., 2002. Guidelines for Drinking Water Quality Standards in Developing Countries.
- Soto, M., Méndez, R., Lema, J.M., 1993. Sodium inhibition and sulphate reduction in the anaerobic treatment of mussel processing wastewaters. *J. Chem. Technol. Biotechnol.* 58 (1), 1–7.
- Spain, 2007. Real Decreto 1620/2007 De 7 Diciembre, Por El Que Se Establece El Régimen Jurídico De La Reutilización De Las Aguas.

- Sridang, P.C., Kaiman, J., Pottier, A., Wisniewski, C., 2006. Benefits of MBR in seafood wastewater treatment and water reuse: study case in southern part of Thailand. *Desalination* 200, 712–714.
- Stahel, W.R., 2016. Circular economy: a new relationship with our goods and materials. *Nature*.
- Stevens, J.R., Newton, R.W., Thlusty, M., Little, D.C., 2018. The rise of aquaculture by-products: increasing food production, value, and sustainability through strategic utilisation. *Mar. Pol.* 90, 115–124.
- Stone, E.F., Barnett, H.J., Hunter, P.J., Roberts, G.C., Nelson, R.W., 1981. Processing wastewater from two mechanized salmon canneries. *Mar. Fish. Rev.* 43 (1), 21–25.
- Tamburini, E., Turolla, E., Fano, E.A., Castaldelli, G., 2020. Sustainability of mussel (*Mytilus galloprovincialis*) farming in the Po river delta, northern Italy, based on a life cycle assessment approach. *Sustainability* 12 (9), 3814.
- Tay, J.H., Show, K.Y., Hung, Y.T., 2004. Seafood processing wastewater treatment. In: *Handbook of Industrial and Hazardous Wastes Treatment*. CRC Press, pp. 706–749.
- Taylor, P., Tacon, A.G.J., Metian, M., Lam, L.D.A., Oceanográfico, I., Paulo, U.D.S., 2013. Reviews in fisheries science fish matters : importance of aquatic foods in human nutrition and global food supply fish matters. *Importance of Aquatic Foods in Human Nutrition and Global* 37–41. July 2014.
- Tilsworth, T., Morgan Jr., J.D., 1983. Alaska seafood processing industry. In: *Proc. 38th Ind. Waste Conf. (Lafayette, IN)*. UN, 2024. United Nations. Available at: <https://www.un.org/en>.
- Venugopal, V., Sasidharan, A., 2021. Seafood industry effluents: environmental hazards, treatment and resource recovery. *J. Environ. Chem. Eng.* 9 (2), 104758.
- Venzke, C.D., Giacobbo, A., Ferreira, J.Z., Bernardes, A.M., Rodrigues, M.A.S., 2018. Increasing water recovery rate of membrane hybrid process on the petrochemical wastewater treatment. *Process Saf. Environ. Prot.* 117, 152–158.
- Vo, H.N.P., Ngo, H.H., Guo, W., Chang, S.W., Nguyen, D.D., Chen, Z., et al., 2020. Microalgae for saline wastewater treatment: a critical review. *Crit. Rev. Environ. Sci. Technol.* 50 (12), 1224–1265.
- Walsh, 2020. Waste Remediation and Value Creation: the Recovery of Nutrients from Dairy Industry Wastewater Using the Aquatic Plant *Lemna minor*. PhD thesis. University College Cork.
- Walsh, É., Margassery, L., Coughlan, N., Broughton, R., Kühnhold, H., Fricke, A., et al., 2022. Innovative Valorisation of Dairy Processing Wastewater Using a Circular Economy Approach (Newtrients) (No. 441). Report.
- Welsh, F.W., Zall, R.R., 1979. Fish Scales: a Coagulating Aid for the Recovery of Food Processing Wastewater Colloids. New York Sea Grant Institute, Albany, N.Y.
- Wu, X.Y., Yang, Y.F., 2011. Heavy metal (Pb, Co, Cd, Cr, Cu, Fe, Mn and Zn) concentrations in harvest-size white shrimp *Litopenaeus vannamei* tissues from aquaculture and wild source. *J. Food Compos. Anal.* 24 (1), 62–65.
- Yasseen, B.T., Al-Thani, R.F., 2022. Endophytes and halophytes to remediate industrial wastewater and saline soils: perspectives from Qatar. *Plants* 11 (11), 1497.
- Zhou, Y., Borisjuk, N., 2019. Small aquatic duckweed plants with big potential for the production of valuable biomass and wastewater remediation. *Int. J. Environ. Sci. Nat. Resour.* 16, 555942.
- Ziminska, H., 1985. Protein recovery from fish wastewaters, agricultural waste utilization and management. In: *Proc. 5th Int. Symp. on Agricultural Wastes*. Chicago, IL.
- Zuo, Y., Zhan, J., Costa, N., 2001. Use of shell chitin extracted from seafood processing waste in recycling of industrial wastewater. *Environmentally Conscious Manufacturing* 4193, 403–412. SPIE.